

Fault tolerance in distributed database systems

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Abstract : Pioneer networked systems assume that connections are reliable, and a faulty operation will be considered in case of losing a connection. Transient connections are typical of mobile devices. Areas of application of data sharing system such as these, lead to the conclusion that network connections may not always be reliable, and that the conventional approaches can be improved. Nigerian commercial banking industry is a critical system whose operation is increasingly becoming dependent on information technology (IT) driven information system. The proposed solution to this problem makes use of a hierarchically clustered network structure which we selected to reflect (as much as possible) the typical organizational structure of the Nigerian commercial banks. Representative transactions such as data updates and replication of the results of such updates were used to simulate the proposed model to show its applicability.

Keywords : Dependability, reliability, data redundancy

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014